

ISSN electrynico: 2172-9077

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17555424>

CODE-SWITCHING AMONG SAUDI INFLUENCERS IN SOCIAL MEDIA: A CASE STUDY TOWARD DOCUMENTING PATTERNS OF ARABIC DIGLOSSIA

Ahmed Saad Almutiri*

Imam Mohammad Ibn Saud Islamic University, Saudi Arabia. ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-1730-0621>, Email: asalmutiri@imamu.edu.sa

Fecha de recepciyn de la resaca: 12 April 2025

Fecha de aceptaciyn definitiva: 29 December 2025

Abstract

This study investigates code-switching patterns among Saudi influencers on social media platforms, specifically Snapchat and X (formerly Twitter), to document aspects of Arabic diglossia. Employing a descriptive methodology, the research observed the posts and snaps of six Saudi influencers over a one-month period, analyzing their use of Standard Arabic (SA) and Saudi Dialect (SD) in various contextual situations. Findings reveal that the choice between SA and SD is primarily influenced by stance, audience, and persona, rather than a clear distinction between platforms. influencers tend to employ SA in serious, logical, and scientific discourse, while SD is predominantly used for humor, sarcasm, and jest, irrespective of the platform's modality (written on X or oral on Snapchat). Nevertheless, a secondary pattern suggests a general inclination for SD use on Snapchat and SA on X among most influencers. Code-switching, predominantly from SA to SD, frequently occurs to address specific topics (e.g., sports), attract younger audiences, engage in humor, accommodate interlocutors, or simplify relative pronouns, with the latter being a universal practice across all influencers' Snapchat content. Interestingly, when speakers opt for SA on Snapchat, their speech rate is notably slower than when using SD. Furthermore, specific personae, such as (MR) and (SAS), consistently utilize SA due to their self-presentation as a religious/conservative figure and a highly professional journalist, respectively. This research highlights the dynamic and context-dependent nature of code choice and code-switching in Saudi social media discourse.

Keywords: Code-Switching, Arabic Diglossia, Saudi Dialect, Standard Arabic, Social Media, Snapchat, X (Twitter).

1. INTRODUCTION

This study is interested in discovering the phenomenon of diglossia in Saudi Arabia among Saudi speakers. In specific, how Saudis interact with each other in both online written application (X) and

in online communicative applications (Snapchat). In Saudi Arabia, people speak natively the Saudi Dialect (SD). Such a dialect is known to be the low variety, while the standard Arabic used in formal speech and written statements is known as the high variety (Ferguson, 1959).

In Arabic, there are many colloquial Arabic varieties divided based on the Arabic countries, as in Egypt and Saudi Arabia. Badawi (1973) divided Arabic in Egypt into five levels: Classical Arabic (CA), Modern Standard Arabic (MSA), Egyptian Colloquial Arabic (ECA).

Only (CA) and (MSA) are acquired in schools as high variety language, whereas (ECA) is acquired as the mother tongue. Nevertheless, the written system is attested and organized for only (CA) and (MSA), while (ECA) derived its written form, recently, from the formal language (CA/MSA), since the phonemic sounds are almost identical, the orthographic symbols of (CA) can be used to represent the colloquial speech. (CA) has been known as the language of the holy Arabic book (Qur'an) as well as the classical literature books, while (MSA) is the language of modern literature books and journals. The main difference is that Classical Arabic (CA) is case-sensitive with vowel endings changing based on the word's syntactic function, a feature absent in Modern Standard Arabic (MSA).

The morphemic marker changes depend on the syntactic function in the sentence, as in /kitaab/ 'book-ROOT' > [kitaabun] 'book-NOMINATIVE or [kitaaban] 'book-ACCUSITIVE' or [kitaabin] 'book-GENITIVE "in (CA)" > [kitaab] 'book-in all syntactic functions of (MSA).

The divergent between the language levels of varieties triggers the switch between these levels and styles during the speech to show prestige, high socioeconomic level and education (Kosoff, 2014; Versteegh, 1997).

1.1. Background

Having stated the variety in Saudi Arabia, the switch between the varieties is attested. Cod-Switching (CS) is defined as the switch between two different varieties within one discourse (Myers-Scotton & Jake, 2009). The original variety in the discourse is categorized as the matrix language, and the other variety that carries the switches is categorized as the embedded language (Myers-Scotton & Jake, 2009). CS occurs in speech for purposes, such as addressee accommodation and persona or identity reflection, as well as social solidarity and for other purposes (Bentahila, 1983; Giles et al., 1987). The first two purposes of CS might be occurred in Saudi Arabian community while the social solidarity could be absent at least in open wide sources like X and Snapchat, since the current study assumes a degree of social homogeneity among the observed influencers, which may limit the applicability of 'social solidarity' as a primary motive for code-switching, unlike in contexts with more pronounced social stratification. Saeed (1997) showed that CS in religious discourse from the formal code (SA) to three different Arabic dialects in Kuwait, Yamen and Egypt. He found that the switches from (SA) to the dialects occur as a sort of speech simplification.

Albirini (2011) examined participants from different Arabic dialects (Saudi, Levantine and Egyptian) when participating in talk show programs divided by the subject of these talk shows as: religious, political, and soccer competitions. These subjects represent, as he assumed, the high variety, mixed, and low variety, respectively.

He asserted that the motivation toward the switch from dialects to (SA) is mostly depended on the importance of the context, how serious the subject is, showing prestigious identity (persona), as well as using historical expressions derived from Classical Arabic. These expressions are similar to '*God Bless You, Oh My God!*'. They are identical in phonations and structures. In my opinion, however, these expressions should be considered part of a shared linguistic code, and therefore do not constitute an actual switch, since they are common to both high and low varieties.

In contrast, Albirini (2011) found that the switch into the dialects is accompanied with less important discourse (comic phrases), less prestigious discourse (taboo words, daily life phrases), and accessible

speech (simplifying the high variety form). Therefore, while the discourse is a key factor, the speaker's stance is an equally important trigger for code-switching. That is, whenever the speaker found the word, or the phrase needs to be in dialects, he would switch disregarding the fact that the subject is religious. This is because the speaker thinks the audiences are less educated or even he needs to criticize some behaviors in sarcastic way.

Alzahrani (2025) conducted a quantitative study of CS based on self-reported methodology among the participants who are bilinguals of Arabic-English. He found that CS depends on the audience, topic, and persona. He also found that socio-biographical factor plays a role in CS.

1.2. The Current Study

This study observes Saudi famous influencers in social media who have both X and Snapchat accounts, in order to find when they use (SA) variety, or (SD) variety, and when they switch from one to the other. Saudis are considered to be in middle economic class, and it is difficult to find someone from low class participating in social media, therefore the style, persona, stance and solidarity (in different usage) may affect the speech code.

It should be mentioned that Saudis speak natively their (SD), while they acquire (SA) from the initial year of the elementary schools. Thus, they are fluent in (SA) specially in writing.

In writing, they write in (SA) traditionally, nevertheless they started to write (type) in SD since the internet chatting channels appeared around 2000s. This is almost similar to German and Swiss-German (Siebenhaar 2006). However, this is not an issue since the written system of Arabic is almost identical to phonetic elements. That is, typing is according to what you hear, and the written symbols used in (SD) are also identical to (SA). No previous studies, as far as I know, conducted a comparison between (CS) in writing-based application (as in X) vs oral-based application (as in Snapchat). In case of Standard German and Swiss-German, Siebenhaar (2006) found that people seem very active in writing the dialects in Swiss-German in online chatting application than in Standard German. The research questions of the current study are as the following: Do they retain the standard language in social media? Do they speak and write in social media (Snapchat, X) with one code (standard/dialect)? If they switch from standard to dialect, when do they switch and what causes them to do so?

2. METHODOLOGY

I selected 6 Saudi influencers, each one has account in both X and Snapchat, in order to answer the previous questions. Every influencer has particular characteristics that differ from the others. In my results, I will start with brief introduction for everyone's characteristic whenever I present his data, to illustrate their social background and behaviors.

I observed the influencers' posts and snaps for about one month. X is a documented source, that is everyone can review old and new posts for influencers, while this is not the case with Snapchat, since the snaps will disappear after one day or a few days from the initial time of publishing them, so I observed their snaps as well as some snaps that their fans save them in YouTube. I excluded the repetition patterns of posts, that is similar code switching in similar situation, in order to keep this project within the limit. In order to guarantee scientific research ethics, I provided codes for every participant as the following order: (AM), (SAS), (ABL), (MR), (NH) and (NM). Also, I excluded any negative identification of a company or an institution by typing three dots (...) which I obligated to use only once in the current research. The data collection of posts and snaps are saved for analysis, then in descriptive method at the result section below, I will provide for each speaker his posts/snaps translated in English, then I will start to describe everyone speech's code if he uses (SA) or (SD) accompanied with description of the post/

snap contextual situation in order to determine the social effect of speech choice or Code-switch. The social effect would be the audience, stance and persona.

It should be mentioned that (SD) differs from (SA) in word choice and some syntactic elements. However, there are some identical words in both varieties. Therefore, if the context in the sentence does not provide differentiation between the varieties I ignored the post entirely. Mostly, from few words of the posts or the snaps it is easy as a native speaker to determine the variety, and then the switch. I used the square bracket [] labeled as the actual phonetic articulation for the influencer, while I used the slashes /./ to represent the phonemic input, as utilized in phonetics and phonology.

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The first influencer is a soccer journalist (AM), in his 40s, and a big fan of Al-Nasser team, he has users in both X and Snapchat:

AM.1) X: The discourse situation after Al-Nasser defeated Al-Hilal (the competitor team): Al-Nasser president is very happy, and he said in short video: "We took the lead of the league (forefront) from Al-Hilal *Forcibly*"

(AM) wrote to make fun of Al-Hilal fans and followers: "Though I am an old journalist, I did not get what the president meant! Anyone can explain to me?"

In the first post above, he wrote in Saudi dialect (SD) and the marker of such a dialect appears in the word choices that he selected, such as [bas] for /laakin/ 'but' and [wish] for /maa.paa/ 'what'. This is in a dialectal context of making fun of the competitors, and this is suitable to make the joke much stronger than if he just wrote it in standard Arabic (SA).

From this post, he did not show a switch from (SD) to (SA), since the context is sarcastic and also the discourse is about the soccer competences.

AM.2) X: The situation is about the same competence between both teams: (Al-Nasser and Al-Hilal): and he wrote:

"If you want to know how strong and majestic Al-Nasser is, take a look at some Hilali journalists and fans, they had wishes to lead the league by gab points of +9 then they changed it to +6 and +2 from the nearest competitor team in the league (Al-Nasser). Now, they proud of having just one goal in a game they lost (2-3) after they ended down -1 points. It is Al-Nasser prestige".

In the second post above, he started a post without reaction of a joke. He needs to take a step up to show prestigious discourse to convince the followers (Al-Nasser's and Al-Hilal's fans) by logic context, he needs to say *listen to me I am now serious and honest, and you can figure out by yourself*. Therefore, he used standard Arabic (SA).

AM.3) X: The situation is to criticize Al-Hilal fans and to make fun of them as well as some of Al-Hilal journalists:

"A supporter is laying down on a couch eating pumpkin seed and criticizing one of the best coaches around the world (he means Al-Hilal coach), and what makes me angry some of the journalists who mimicking what the fans say, only to say for the fans: see us we are in agreement with your opinions"

In (AM.3) the audiences are different, one should be high professional soccer analysts (Al-Hilal journalists) and the second readers are supposed to be low professional analysts (the fans). The post is totally in Saudi dialect, but he switched to standard Arabic only in one word in order to express the stupidity of the journalists who follow the fans without awareness, this is in: [jan.saa.quuna. xal.fa.hum] 'walking after someone "Verb"'. This idiom is basically used in classical Arabic for the sheep when following

the shepherd". In this case of the switch he wants to use a formal word to remind the professional journalist that they were in reverse, instead of being leaders for the fans they became followers to them.

AM.4) X: "This information is important to you as Al-Nasser fan: since Petros [*a player for Al-Nasser who did well during the match*] took the bus yesterday after the match (Al-Nasser vs Al-Hilal) he was crying until he arrives to his car, and no one succeeded to stop him. He was playing from the bottom of his brave heart".

In (AM.4) he is writing this post for Al-Nasser fans and he wrote it as literary texts in order to attract their emotional attention. This is totally in (SA) to convince the followers by high variety code. In X, when he started news or statistical votes in order to make the followers to participate, he uses the standard Arabic, while if he wants to make jokes he usually writes in Saudi dialect.

In Snapchat, whenever (AM) meets fans he speaks always in Saudi dialect, while when he speaks to the followers he mixes between the SA and the SD. In details, he speaks generally (SA) with some switching to (SD). That is, when taking zoom into his codes he switches relative pronouns (who, that, which) and demonstratives (this) from (SA) to (SD). This is because the relative pronouns and demonstratives in (SD) has phonological simplification from (SA) to (SD). For example: [ʔil.li] from /ʔal.la.pi/ 'who' and [haa.pi] and [pi] /haa.pi.hi/ 'this'. As you could notice that the (SA) codes have three syllables while the (SD) codes have less than that. It should be mentioned that, whenever he slows the speech rate down he increases the uses of (SA) codes due to the difficulty of speaking (SA) subconsciously without preparation. The second influencer is (SAS), in his 60s, he is also a soccer journalist who is well-known in media (guest in TV show and he is active in social media).

In X, the situation is that he is criticizing Al-Hilal Club since the president of Al-Hilal blamed the Saudi Arabian Football Federation by saying that they did not even congratulate us for reaching the final in Arab Club Championship, while he gained financial aid from them.

SAS. 1) X: "After they *Swallow* the millions (the money) that they did not admit they received, they are now looking for a phrase of 'congrats!'"

In this tweet, he used clearly (SA) variety. Also, he used the Standard form of the relative pronoun [ʔal.lati] 'that', which is usually in spoken speech represented as the Saudi form /ʔal.li/.

SAS. 2) X: "This man in the picture below is *The Phenomenon* that nobody can break his luck"

SAS. 3) X: In X to Al-Nasser fans: "you were a subject of people talk during the *derby* [*a strong soccer match between two famous clubs in Saudi Arabia (Al-Nasser vs Al-Hilal)*]. your team lead is your responsibility for the next match. Al-Nasser deserves the best.

In the above two posts, he used (SA) even if he was trying to attract the fans to get the tickets to attend the match to support Al-Nasser. However, he switched into (SD) at the end of the tweet as the following: [ʔan.na.sr. jis.taa.hil] 'Al-Nasser deserves' instead of (SA) /ʔan.na.ssr. jas.ta.hiqq/. This switch is linguistically at the level of word choice since the equal word in (SA) to (SD) is completely different word, and not only they differ in one or two phonetic elements.

My explanation of the switch at the end of the post is that, at first, he wants to identify himself as professional educated journalist, but he needed to switch to (SD) in order to encourage the fans (usually youth) to support their team. Over 35 posts from him, I did not notice any further switches from (SA) to (SD). In Snapchat, I observed him during one month, and he is almost in every instance of the relative pronoun (that) uses SD form which is [ʔal.li] instead of SA form /ʔal.la.ti/. Similarly, another relative pronoun 'which', he selected the SD form [ʔin.nu] 'which' instead of the

SA form /ʔan.nahu/. As I illustrated above, this kind of switch is a sort of simplifying the phonetic elements of the SA into SD form, and this is apparent in which the SD form has less phonetic elements and syllables than the SA form. As a result, it is easy to pronounce during rapid speech. While in X, he writes this type of switch in SA since the writing system in Arabic is simple and at most, what you pronounce of phonemic consonants and long vowels have specific orthographic symbols. This suggests that a slower pace of writing provides an opportunity to choose a more formal variety, while the rapid nature of spoken conversation encourages simplification and consequently code-switching. It should be mentioned that in the Arabic written form, SA still has more orthographic symbols than SD in this type of switch. For example, the SA /ʔal.la.ti/ is formed orthographically as “4 = ”التي symbols, while in the SD [ʔal.li] is formed as “3 = ”الي symbols. Nevertheless, although the availability of SD written forms, (SAS) writes his posts in this particular type of switch in SA form, and at the same time, he pronounces this switch in his snaps in SD. Therefore, simplifying the expression is preferable in speech rather than in writing.

The third influencer is (ABL), in his 40s, he is a famous lawyer who has been known as a liberal, and he is usually goes in strong arguments with conservative people in the society criticizing aspect of religious believes, and community's traditional norms and behaviors.

In X, whenever he writes a post to express his political opinion and human rights he writes in SA. If he wants to make fun of opponents or if he wants to write about his opinion in sports and matches he writes in SD. In general, in serious situation he writes in SA and when joking he writes in SD even in one post he can switch between them depends on how serious the context is. For example;

ABL. 1) “To my brother who wants to go to the match, be in your team seat, and do not listen to the instigators to make a miss, because they will not protect you from being in charge for violating the rules. Be aware that it is just a match for fun and it is not the end of life. Be strongly also aware without doubt that Hamdallah's goal is a legal goal”

In this post, Al-Hilal fans said that they will take some seats in Al-nasser grandstand during the match. He wants to warn them from doing that by stating the rules in SA then he switched into SD to make fun of them since he supports Al-Nasser by stating that “Hamdallah's goal is a legal goal”, Hamdallah is a player for Al-Nasser who scored a goal earlier during the league and Al-Hilal fans said this score is a foul and it illegal.

In the Snapchat when he speaks to his followers, he speaks friendly in informal speech SD except when he speaks about the history of the constitution and amendment he switched to SA. He also, simplifies the relative pronouns and demonstratives into SD. Also, in some word choices such as in [gaf.fa.lat] for /ʔay.la.qat/ ‘closed V’ in this sentence: “The government closed their shops, the uvular /q/ is less common in SD speech and it is simplified into the velar stop /g/. The fourth influencer is (MR), in his 30s, who is a famous influencer on saying advices and wisdoms for the community, and many people has an implication that he is conservative and religious, which is a positive attitude in Saudi society.

He usually posts in SA while in Snapchat he speaks in SD. In details, he posts generally in SA to show that he is religious, and he is educated and influencer for the community. While he switched into SD if he posts about sports and fans. The difference between the SA and SD in his posts is the words choice, such as in [jaa.milh.ʔan.nasʳ.ra.wi.jiin] ‘look how sweet Al-Nasser fans are’, in SA is /ma.ʔadʒ.ma.la.ʔan.nasʳ.ra.wi.jiin/. It is the same meaning with different words. In Snapchat he speaks most of the time in SD even when he speaks about academic situation in Saudi universities. This is because it is difficult to him to speak rapidly without

careful preparation in SA as explained above. Also, whenever he speaks to the followers in SD, I assume he feels that he needs to show solidarity in terms of *I am close to you*, so I am speaking your native dialect.

The Fifth influencer is funny and strange, (NH), in his 20s, is a guy who became famous in Snapchat since he started to tell old stories that had been written in classical Arabic, but he retells them in SD and even most of the time in his vernacular dialect (Bedouins' dialects) which they are well-known as the lowest variety of SD. He succeeded to attract thousands of followers by using his vernacular dialect.

In X, he is not very active, though he posts in SD, since in written form the Bedouins' dialects differ from SD only in the level of phonetic elements and in a few words. For example: [ʔil.kum] in Bedouins' dialects /likum/ in SD 'for you all' and [pi.gih] vs /puu.gah/ 'taste it-Imperative verb'. Therefore, he did not show a switch into SA at any discoursed situation. Also, he is young and the standard speech does not represent younger speakers even in chatting application as stated by Siebenhaar (2006). The Sixth influencer is (NM), in his late 30s, he is a famous influencer whose well-known as a socio-political sarcastic influencer, he usually makes fun of political leaders and journalists.

NM.1) X: In Pinned post, he wrote his post totally in SA. This post is written to criticize one of the users in post who writes under hidden nickname (...).

He wrote: "#the story of (...): In this hashtag and this thread, I will write about (...) account: analyzing contents, behaviors, in order to clearly identify this account, and asking questions".

This post and his thread is the only post I found in his posts that are totally in SA, since he is writing this in formal status and in serious language.

NM.2) X: "We have been warning about the dangerous situations in that specific country. In order to prove that, look at its TV Channel, it has been crying!"

He wrote this tweet after he posted a video for the TV Channel criticizing his posts about the situation in that country. The specific TV channel he mentioned is in political alignment with that country's government, and (NM) describes the security situation there as bad status and dangerous. The tweet is totally in SD, and from his way of making fun of the channel as he is obviously criticizing them, he used the SD word [sʕaa.hat] 'cried' instead of SA /sʕa.ra.xat/. People usually make jokes in their actual daily life speech, and this is definitely not in SA.

NM.3) X: He is presenting videos of his snaps about a meeting with an employee for BMW car company to do a commercial advertisement. He posts: "An opening ceremony for BMW X7 in Saudi Arabia, this car has 7 seats. The full announcement will be in Snapchat".

This post is totally in SA, and the relative pronoun (which) is clearly in SA, while in his snaps of this particular subject (BMW Advertisement), he speaks in SD. In the same snaps for this subject he started greetings in SA and he switched into SD during his first sentence to introduce the employee by simplifying the relative pronoun (which) into SD as explained earlier. Then he continued to complete his speech in SD. Also, the employee started the meeting by greetings SA then he switched into SD.

I assume that SA is a language of reading and writing in Saudi Arabia, and Saudis, as mentioned above, acquire this high variety from schools, so it is difficult for many people to master a full conversation in SA, while it is easier in writing since the writer has time to think and proof his writing, while in conversation the speech is live. Moreover, this example provides great indication when the subject, the audience and the stance are identical. Therefore, in this case, the written

application (X) could be in SA, and the oral application (Snapchat) could be in SD. Standard Arabic has been known as the language of formal discourse, and this definitely includes the written system, since people have been using writing only for official and formal situations as writing letters, faxes, documents, and E-mails. Until the early 2000s, in Saudi Arabia people started to text short messages by cellphones in SD, and this is not to public. After the massive spread of using internet websites, 20 years ago, they have started to write in SD in chat forums but under unknown names (nicknames-hidden identity) to interact with girls/boys, to say taboo words without being stigmatized or charged. Therefore, the use of SD in writing was seen for informal situations. Then, the origin stance is that Saudis write in SA and they speak in both varieties for purposes.

Despite the fact that I did not find a previous study to discover the usage of SA and SD by highlighting CS, Alzahrani (2025) found that Saudi Arabic-English bilinguals switched between Arabic and English based on audience, topic, and persona as he stated interlocuter role and stance. Unfortunately, he did not mention which code the participants would switch to. Therefore, it is difficult to determine the dominant code over the other. Also, he admits in the limitation of his study that self-reported study by the participants may lead to biased results. Hence, the qualitative case study based on the observation and analysis of actual, spontaneous language use by six Saudi influencers. That is, while his study establishes that speakers are aware that context affects their code-switching, the current study goes a step further by showing how this happens in real-time, online communication. It provides concrete observable evidence of the specific patterns and triggers of code-switching that the Alzahrani (2025) study's methodology may not have captured.

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, there is no clear boundary for code choice between Snapchat and X, as the decision is primarily dictated by contextual factors such as stance, audience, and persona. That is, whenever the influencer addresses his speech in serious, logic and scientific situation he tends to choose the SA, while if he addresses his speech to make fun of others, stigmatize and making jokes, he uses the SD regardless of the platform's modality, whether it is writing-based (X) or oral-based (Snapchat). Nevertheless, it seems that, for most of the influencers, in Snapchat they tend to speak SD, while in X they write in SA, and this could be the secondary effect of code choice. In terms of Code-Switching, most of the switches occur when speech suddenly shifts from SA to SD for purposes such as: the subject (particularly sports), attracting young fans, making fun of others, accommodation, matching the addressee code and simplifying the relative pronoun, as mentioned above. The latter is applied on all the influencers in their snaps. This study also found that when a speaker chooses to use SA on Snapchat, their speech rate is notably slower than when they speak in SD, a finding that contrasts with the simplifying nature of dialectal speech. In terms of personae, (MR) and (SAS) always tend to post in SA, since the former presents himself as a religious and a conservative, while the latter represents himself as highly professional journalist.

4.1. Research Funding

This work was supported and funded by the Deanship of Scientific Research at Imam Mohammad Ibn Saud Islamic University (IMSIU) (Grant Number: IMSIU-DDRSP2502).

REFERENCES

- Albirini, A. (2011). The sociolinguistic functions of codeswitching between Standard Arabic and Dialectal Arabic. *Language in Society*, 40(5), 537-562. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0047404511000674>
- Alzahrani, S. A. (2025). Does Context Affect Code-Switching? A Case Study of Saudi Arabic Self-Reported Code-Switchers. *Fonseca Journal of Communication*, 29(1), 105-127. <https://revistas-fonseca.com/index.php/2172-9077/article/view/718>
- Badawi, A. S. M. (1973). *Mustanayat al-Arabiya al-mu'asira fi Misr* [Levels of Contemporary Arabic in Egypt]. Cairo: Dar Al-Ma'arif.
- Bentahila, A. (1983). Motivations for Code-Switching Among Arabic-French Bilinguals in Morocco. *Language & Communication*, 3(3), 233-243. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0271-5309\(83\)90003-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0271-5309(83)90003-4)
- Ferguson, C. A. (1959). Diglossia. *Word*, 15(2), 325-340. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00437956.1959.11659702>
- Giles, H., Mulac, A., Bradac, J. J., & Johnson, P. (1987). Speech Accommodation Theory: The First Decade and Beyond. In M. McLaughlin (Ed.), *Communication Yearbook* (Vol. 10, pp. 13-48). Beverly Hills, CA: Sage.
- Kosoff, Z. (2014). Code-Switching in Egyptian Arabic: A Sociolinguistic Analysis of Twitter. *Al-Arabiyya*, 47, 83-99. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/24635374>
- Myers-Scotton, C., & Jake, J. (2009). A Universal Model of Code-Switching and Bilingual Language Processing and Production. In B. E. Bullock & A. J. Toribio (Eds.), *The Cambridge Handbook of Linguistic Code-Switching* (pp. 336-357). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511576331.020>
- Saeed, A. T. A. (1997). *The Pragmatics of Codeswitching From Fusha Arabic to Aammiyyah Arabic in Religious-Oriented Discourse* [Doctoral dissertation, Ball State University]. <https://liblink.bsu.edu/catkey/1063206>
- Siebenhaar, B. (2006). Code choice and code-switching in Swiss-German Internet Relay Chat rooms. *Journal of Sociolinguistics*, 10(4), 481-506. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9841.2006.00289.x>
- Versteegh, K. (1997). *The Arabic Language*. Columbia University Press.